

Analytic - Simulation Approaches of a Robust Procedure: An Alternative to the Classical Statistical Matching Method

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ABSTRACT

Two files A and B are to be statistically matched. File A contains n records $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n$ and file B contains a similar number of records $B_1, B_2, \dots, B_n$. The records in file B are the same records found in file A but are considered updated records. It is desired to match the records in file B with those in file A. The study compared the performance of the classical statistical matching procedure using a Mahalanobis distance function with a robust record timing procedure when data sets contain outliers or gross errors. Theoretical analytic results reveal that the trimmed Mahalanobis distance method outperforms the classical statistical matching procedure measured in terms of correct matches. Simulation results, on the other hand, confirm the superiority of the trimmed record method over the classical statistical matching.

Keywords: Statistical Matching, Robust Statistics, Mahalanobis Distance Function, Simulation, Outliers

INTRODUCTION

Consider the following version of a statistical matching problem: two files A and B are to be matched. File A contains n records $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n$ and file B contains a similar number of records $B_1, B_2, \dots, B_n$. The records in file B are the same records found in file A but are considered updated records. It is desired to match the records in file B with those in file A. It is also possible that some of the records in file A contain incomplete information, hence, merging these records

with those in file B would be desirable. Each record $A_i(B_i)$ contains informative variables $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p$ about an individual.

There are various instances in which statistical matching would be useful. The recent fire that gutted the NCR office of the National Census and Statistics Office (NCSO) for instance, destroyed some updated records of individuals but portions of these records had been rescued and are now being reconciled with past records of the individuals in other offices. This activity requires knowledge of statistical matching (NCSO, 2006). As another instance in which statistical matching would be useful, we could look at the problem of identifying fatalities in a plane crash, as in the ill-fated Cebu Pacific flight in Cagayan de Oro City some years back. One could theoretically match anthropomorphic measurements of the remains with existing records of passengers listed on the flight manifest in order to make conclusive matching of the individuals listed and the information gathered from post-mortem analysis.

The classical statistical matching procedure consist of finding the minimum Mahalanobis distance between the multivariate vector X in file A with those of the multivariate vector Y in file B, i.e. X and Y are considered matched if the Mahalanobis distance:

$$D = (X - Y)' \Sigma^{-1} (X - Y),$$

is a minimum. Here, Σ is the covariance matrix of $(X - Y)$. In particular, if X and Y are multivariate normal vectors with zero mean vectors, then D obeys a central chi-square distribution with $\text{rank}(\Sigma)$ as degrees of freedom. The classical procedure proceeds by testing the hypothesis that $\min. D = 0$ through the chi-square statistic (1). If $D > \chi^2_{\alpha}$, where χ^2_{α} is the upper $(1-\alpha)$ th percentile point of a chi-square distribution with p degrees of freedom, then the hypothesis is rejected.

A serious problem with using the classical procedure above arises when some of the variables in the records of file B (or file A) are contaminated or corrupted. The Mahalanobis distance (1) is shown to be easily distorted by the presence of gross outliers in the data (Huber, 1981; Padua, 1989). Thus, in the presence of gross outliers, one may mistakenly conclude a match when in fact there is none or conclude that there is no match when in fact there is.

In this paper, we explore an alternative to the classical statistical matching procedure. The alternative being considered here uses a trimmed distance function (or the Huber's function). In the univariate setting of estimating a location parameter

of a probability distribution $f(x,\theta)$, the trimmed mean has been found to be a satisfactory alternative to the sample mean in the sense of maintaining a high level of efficiency whilst at the same time providing protection against the unwanted influence of gross observations (Huber, 1981; Padua, 1989).

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Rodgers, et.al.(1980) investigated the inherent assumption of statistical matching procedure: that the conditional distribution of Y given X is independent on the conditional distribution of Z given X . In this study, two sets of files were generated from the same source, the Income Survey Development Program. One set was the base file (File A), and the other set was considered as the supplemental file (File B). Further, the study used the vector $X = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p)$ as the set of common characteristics to both sets of files, and those variables not common to both files A and B, used $Y = (Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_Q)$ for file A and $Z = (Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_R)$ for file B. The study created a match file of (X, Y, Z) by fusing similar X variables which minimized the distance function by Radner, et. al. (1980), as follows ;

$$D_{ij} = \sum [w_p \times g (X_{ip} - X_{jp})]$$

where w_p is a predefined weight reflecting the importance attached to the p^{th} X variable, and $g(p)$ used were of three types : the absolute difference in the values of the X variable; the square of the difference; or an indicator variable indicating agreement or disagreement. The inherent assumption implies that the correlation of the Y and Z variables is zero, however, the study generated a set of matched files whose Y - Z correlation differed substantially from the original source. Hence, the study concluded that, analyses made on the matched files are risky.

Gavin(1985), applied statistical matching to create databases for health records researches from the Survey of Income and Education (SIE) and the 1976 Health Interview Survey (HIS). In this study, a composite data record was created by selecting a record from one file (HIS) that best matches a given record on the second file (SIE) and appending information on the second file. Here, the best match was determined by the maximization of a score of the HIS matched variables. The match variables were grouped into stratifications, and each match variable was assigned a certain number of points, of which, the points assigned to each of the match variables were based on their relative importance in determining the information to be appended to the base file. These points were

all accumulated in a total score for each of the HIS records in a cell if that record and the SIE record had the same variable value. The HIS record with the highest total score greater than a minimum allowable value was determined to be the best match. This study showed that, there was no bias in the distribution of the created file using the base file weights, thus, the merged file successfully combines SIE and the HIS files. Gavin emphasized on the application of statistical matching in the creation of a more informative file using the maximization of stratification variables

Sinclair et.al. (2001) used statistical matching to obtain a more detailed household health insurance survey. This study linked data sets from the Followback Survey (File B), containing data from insuring entities on characteristics of specific health plans products they offered, to the data set of the household component of the Community Tracking Survey (File A), containing data on a variety of health care issues, including whether the members of the household were covered by private health insurance and, if so, the characteristics of the health plans. Sinclair used an auxiliary data file of known linkage to develop a statistical matching procedure. The approach of this method consisted of four developmental stages. First, a set attributes from file B (the product file), that appears to most accurately describe the differences among the record on that file, was selected. This selected attribute served as the primary matching variable. Second, from the auxiliary file which contains a set of file A and file B linked data, a series of standard regression models were developed to predict each of the selected items on file B from the items on File A. Third, the model coefficients were used to obtain predicted values for the selected file B items for each of the unlinked file A records. Fourth, the predicted values for each file A record were compared with the values of the file B record. The file B record with the closest set of values was selected as the final linked. The procedure used by Sinclair was validated by using sets of mock data of known matches and having the same distribution as that of file A and file B. With these mock data, the same procedure was performed, and result showed about 63.5% match.

Albacea, et.al.(2006) studied on the empirical evaluation of statistical matching to create panel data sets. In this study, the distributional properties of four distance functions were evaluated and the best form of distance function was that

function whose distributional properties are similar to the distributional properties of the matching variables.

Ingram, et.al.(2008), used partitioning technique, distance measure and predictive mean technique in the statistical match of US March 1996 Current Population Survey (CPS) and 1995 National Health Interview Survey (HNIS). Partitioning involves dividing the records of the two surveys into mutually exclusive subgroups (cells), hence decreasing the size of the original survey variables, and permitting matches between corresponding subgroups. Partitioning is used when matches between certain types of records should be avoided because the characteristics of the individuals are sufficiently dissimilar. Partitioning has the effect of narrowing the distance between the records and allow a tighter fit across the two data sets. Ingram used the Euclidean distance to determine the closeness of records from the two surveys. On the other hand, predictive mean matching refers to the imputation procedures for partially missing data within one survey data. With predictive mean matching, a variable that is available from the two surveys is identified for use as independent variable. Then, regression is carried out using the selected dependent variable and a subset of the variable common to both surveys as independent variables. Predictive values common to both surveys are calculated using the regression coefficients. Records from both surveys are matched using predicted values, and are considered matched when they have the most similar predicted values. The mean of some selected variables of the matched file using the predictive mean technique was very much similar to that of the Donor file (either the March 1996 CPS or the 1995 NHIS files), thus, the predictive mean technique has successfully combined the March 1996 CPS and the 1995 NHIS files.

THE PROBLEM

Consider two files A and B each consisting of n similar records. The records in A are denoted by $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n$ in some order while those in B are denoted by $Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n$ in some other order. The records are p-variate vectors:

$$\begin{aligned} X_i &= (x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{ip}) \\ Y_i &= (y_{i1}, y_{i2}, \dots, y_{ip}), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{aligned}$$

A record X_i in file A corresponds to a record Y_j in file B. For these two records, the Mahalanobis distance (1) is minimum. Starting with a record X_i in file A, the classical procedure proceeds by computing the distance (1) for each Y_k in file B until the smallest distance is found. When the records X (and Y) are assumed to

obey a multivariate normal distribution, then the smallest distance found is then tested for significance i.e. whether $D = 0$ or D is not zero, by using a standard chi-square test. Acceptance of the null hypothesis would then imply that a match has been found (with $(1-\alpha) \times 100\%$ confidence coefficient).

Suppose now that $\beta \times 100\%$ of the variables y_{ik} had been contaminated. In particular, we consider the Tukey's contaminated normal model:

$$F(x) = (1-\beta)N(0,1) + \beta N(\mu, 1) ; 0 < \beta < 1,$$

as the operant model. The typical values of β are 5%, 10%, 20% representing slight, moderate to high levels of contamination of the data set. Under these conditions, we investigate the performance of two statistical matching procedures: the classical procedure and the trimmed distance function by the number of correct matches found by the three procedures.

To embark on the study, we fix our records in file A. The X vectors are 10-dimensional multivariate normal vectors each with zero mean and equi-correlated ($\rho = 0.50$) and unit variance. There are $n = 100$ records in file A. A similar set of $n = 100$ records are placed in file B generated from a 10-variate normal distribution with zero mean and unit variance. Using the classical method for statistical matching, the two files are matched record per record. The matches are noted for reference. With the matches already recorded, the records in file B are then contaminated as follows: First, contaminate 5 (5% of $n = 100$ records) of the last variable y_{10} and perform the three matching procedures; next, contaminate 10 (10% of $n = 100$ records) of the last variable, then 20 (20% of the $n = 100$ records) of the last variable each time performing the matching rules. Second, contaminate the last two variables y_9, y_{10} and proceed as before. Continue these contamination exercises until $y_5, y_6, y_7, y_8, y_9, y_{10}$ are all contaminated. The contaminants are generated from $N(\mu, 1)$ where $\mu = 5, 10, 20$.

ROBUST TRIMMED DISTANCE

Let $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ be iid $f(\cdot)$ and suppose that the order statistics are denoted by :

$$x_{(1)} < x_{(2)} < x_{(3)} < \dots < x_{(n)}.$$

The α -trimmed mean is given by:

$$\bar{x}_{(\text{trim})} = 1/(1-2\alpha)n \sum_{i=[\alpha n]}^{[(1-\alpha)n]} x_{(i)}$$

which essentially trims the lowest $[n\alpha]$ and highest $[(1-\alpha)n]$ order statistics and then averages the remaining observations. The trimmed version of the sample variance then becomes:

$$S_{(\text{trim})}^2 = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x}_{(\text{trim})})^2}{(n-1)}.$$

The asymptotic properties of the sample trimmed mean and sample trimmed variance are properly explored in Staudte (1995). The sample trimmed mean and sample trimmed variance converge to the mean and variance of the uncontaminated underlying population for large n .

Consider now the multivariate random vector $X_k = (x_{k1}, \dots, x_{kp})$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ with population covariance matrix Σ . The sample covariance matrix S is obtained by computing the individual sample variances per variable and putting them on the main diagonal of S while the off-diagonal elements are the sample covariances of the variables. The trimmed estimate of the sample covariance matrix is then given by:

$$S_{\text{trim}} = (s_{(ij)_{\text{trim}}})^2,$$

where the components are the corresponding trimmed variances and covariances. The trimmed Mahalanobis distance function (from the mean vector) is:

$$D_{\text{trim}} = (X - \bar{X})' S_{\text{trim}}^{-1} (X - \bar{X}).$$

For conformable vectors X and Y , the trimmed Mahalanobis distance is:

$$D(X, Y)_{\text{trim}} = (X - Y)' S_{\text{trim}}^{-1} (X - Y),$$

where the trimmed covariance matrix in the middle is the trimmed version of the covariance matrix of $(X - Y)$.

The “trimmed” distance function can be formulated by removing, say, the $[n\alpha]$ extreme records where the records are ordered based on their Euclidean lengths, i.e.

$$\text{Record length} = (y_1^2 + y_2^2 + \dots + y_p^2)^{1/2},$$

and then computing a trimmed covariance matrix based on the formulation above on the remaining records. We shall refer this approach as RECORD TRIMMING METHOD.

Record Trimming Method

We begin our discussion of the record trimming method by a definition:

Definition 1. Let S be the sample $p \times p$ covariance matrix of X . The system's variance or generalized variance of X is $\text{genvar}(X) = \text{Trace}(S)$.

Thus, the generalized variance of a vector X is equal to the sum of the variances of the components of X . One advantage in defining a generalized variance as in Definition 1 is that it is a scalar quantity. In particular, the Mahalanobis distance (1) can be re-written in terms of generalized variances as:

$$D(X,Y) = (X-Y)'(X-Y)/\text{tr}(S) = [(x_1 - y_1)^2 + \dots + x_p - y_p)^2]/\text{tr}(S)$$

In this form, we can more easily visualize the effect of contamination on the Mahalanobis distance.

Suppose that the last variable (y_p) of the k^{th} record Y_k is contaminated by a constant μ , then the sample variance becomes:

$$s_p^2 = \Sigma (y_{pi} - \bar{y}_p - \mu/n)^2/(n-1), i = 1,2,\dots,n, \text{ which simplifies to:}$$

$s_p^2 = \Sigma (y_{pi} - \bar{y}_p)^2 + \mu^2/n(n-1) = s^2 + \mu^2/n(n-1), i = 1,2,\dots,n,$ where s^2 is the original variance of the uncontaminated variable y_p . We write this as Lemma 1.

Lemma 1: Let $X_1, \dots, X_n$ be independent identically distributed p -variate vectors from a distribution $f(\cdot)$. Let S be the sample covariance matrix. If one component of X_k is contaminated by a constant μ , then the generalized variance of the contaminated random vectors is:

$$\text{Tr}(S^*) = \text{Tr}(S) + \mu^2/n(n-1).$$

The following Theorem is an immediate application of this Lemma:

Theorem 1. Under the assumptions in Lemma 1, suppose that one of the components of $[\alpha n]$ records $X_1, \dots, X[\alpha n]$ are contaminated by a constant μ , then,

$$\text{Tr}(S^*) = \text{Tr}(S) + [\alpha n] \mu^2/n(n-1).$$

Lemma 1 and Theorem 1 show that the overall effect of contamination is to increase the denominator of the Mahalanobis distance thereby reducing the distance itself, $D(X,Y)$. Theorem 2 shows that this effect is magnified even more if $m < p$ components are contaminated by constants $\mu_1, \dots, \mu_m$.

Theorem 2. Under the same conditions in Theorem 1 and further that $m < p$ components of the $[\alpha n]$ records are contaminated by constants $\mu_1, \dots, \mu_m$, then,

$$\text{Tr}(S^*) = \text{Tr}(S) + [\alpha n](\mu_1^2 + \dots + \mu_m^2) / n(n-1).$$

While our contamination model does not add a fixed number to a variable in a record (the Tukey model adds a random number), both Theorems 1 and 2 indicate what generally happens to the Mahalanobis distance.

We now analyze the same phenomenon using probabilistic arguments. Let the records X, Y in the two files be *iid* multivariate normal $MVN(0, \Sigma)$. On file B, we contaminate $[\alpha n]$ records with $MVN(\mu, \Sigma)$ randomly according to a Tukey model. We are interested in the distribution of the quadratic form $(X-Y)' \Sigma_{X-Y}^{-1} (X-Y) = D(X, Y)$.

To do this, consider first univariate x, y having the same $N(0, 1)$ distribution. It follows that $(x-y)$ has a normal distribution, $N(0, 2)$. Since the square of a $N(0, 1)$ random variable possesses a chi-square distribution, it follows that:

$$(x - y) / \sqrt{2} \text{ has a } N(0, 1) \text{ distribution} \rightarrow [(x - y) / \sqrt{2}]^2 \text{ has a } \chi_1^2 \text{ distribution.}$$

However, if y were $N(\mu, 1)$ then $[(x - y) / \sqrt{2}]^2$ will have a non-central chi-square distribution with non-centrality parameter equal to $\lambda = \mu^2/2$. The following result is a standard result in Linear Models:

Theorem 3 (Graybill). Let X be multivariate normal $MVN(\mu, \Sigma)$, then: $X' \Sigma^{-1} X$ has a non-central χ^2 distribution with $\text{rank}(\Sigma)$ degrees of freedom. The non-centrality parameter is $\lambda = \mu' \mu/2$.

The effect of the non-centrality parameter λ is to shift the origin this much distance to the right. Let Σ_{X-Y} be the covariance matrix of $(X-Y)$ with X distributed as multivariate normal $MVN(0, \Sigma)$ and Y as $MVN(\mu, \Sigma)$, it follows that:

Corollary 1. Under the above assumptions, the distribution of :
 $D(X, Y) = (X-Y)' \Sigma_{X-Y}^{-1} (X-Y)$ is a non-central chi-square with $\text{df} = \text{rank}(\Sigma_{X-Y})$ and non-centrality parameter $\lambda = \mu' \mu/2$.

Under a record trimming method for statistical matching, the corrupted records are deleted from consideration. The estimate of the covariance matrix, S_{trim} , is then essentially computed from the remaining records. It can be shown that: $S_{\text{trim}} \rightarrow \Sigma_{X-Y}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ by a simple application of the law of large numbers. Thus, using the record trimming procedure, the distribution of $D(X, Y)_{\text{trim}} = (X-Y)' S_{\text{trim}}^{-1} (X-Y)$ is a central chi-square distribution with p degrees of

Theorem 4. Under the conditions of Corollary 1, the probability of accepting a match under D1 is less than the probability of accepting a match under D2.

To see this, let χ_α^2 be the upper α th critical point of a central chi-square distribution. When the value of D2 exceeds this value, the two records X and Y are mismatched. On the other hand, for D1, the critical value is shifted to the left to the point $\chi_\tau^2 = \chi_\alpha^2 - \lambda/n(n-1)$ where λ is the non-centrality parameter. It follows that:

$$P(D2 > \chi_\alpha^2) = \alpha < P(D1 > \chi_\tau^2) = \alpha + \tau.$$

Theoretically, the record trimming procedure should produce more matches than the classical method under the contaminated normal model, i.e., the record trimming procedure rejects fewer matches than the classical procedure.

SIMULATION RESULTS

Initially, File A and File B were identical files containing 100 records each. These records were randomly generated from a 10-variate MVN(0, Σ). The records of File B were matched (record per record) to a record in File A. The matched records were noted since these will be the bases in the determination of matched records when the two procedures of statistical matching were performed on the corrupted file. Then, with a known percentage of the records of File B being contaminated, statistical matching was done between the records of File A and with that of the records of the contaminated File B using the Classical Matching method and the Record Trimmed Matching method.

Table 1 showed the percentage of matches using the 2 methods of matching when 5% of the files were contaminated. Generally, the Trimmed Record method gave higher percentage of matches compared to the Classical Matching. As observed in the Trimmed Record method, the percentage of matches when there was a 5% trimming of files were higher compared to the 10% and 20% trimming and standard error, that is, the standard deviation of the mean, varied from 1.2 to 3.8. However, the percentage of matches decreased as the mean of the contaminants was increased. Table 1, also showed that the Classical Matching method gave matches which were almost identical for the 5%, 10% and 20% trimming, but the percentage of matches decreased as the percentage of the variables being contaminated was increased. On the same column, that is for similar percentage of trimming, the Classical Matching Procedure has

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contaminated was increased. It was also observed in table 1 that at 5% of the files being contaminated column, the average of the matched records of the Trimmed Record which is equal to 72%, with standard error on the average equal to 3, has a greater difference compared to the other method, the Classical method, with an average of percentage of matches equal to 51%, and with standard error on the average equal to 2. This implies that the Trimmed Record method performs better, when the percentage of files being contaminated was the same as the percentage of files trimmed than when the percentage of contaminated files was not the same as the percentage of files trimmed.

Table 1. 5% of the Files Being Contaminated

%M – Percentage of Matched Records, SE - Standard Error of the Mean

Percent of Variables Being Contaminated	Distribution of Contaminants	5 % of Files Trimmed				10 % of Files Trimmed				20 % of Files Trimmed			
		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method	
		% M	SE	% M	SE	% M	SE	% M	SE	% M	SE	% M	SE
10	<i>N(5,1)</i>	62	1.9	74	2.1	65	1.9	67	2.0	63	1.7	58	2.5
	<i>N(10,1)</i>	51	2.8	74	3.8	53	2.2	64	2.5	52	2.3	62	1.8
	<i>N(20,1)</i>	45	2.4	70	1.8	46	2.0	65	2.5	50	2.1	63	3.0
20	<i>N(5,1)</i>	58	2.1	75	2.1	53	3.6	65	3.3	53	2.0	61	2.4
	<i>N(10,1)</i>	54	1.5	76	2.5	48	1.8	60	3.5	49	2.3	62	1.4
	<i>N(20,1)</i>	54	2.0	74	3.2	54	3.1	66	1.7	49	3.1	60	2.6
30	<i>N(5,1)</i>	53	3.1	68	2.4	53	1.6	63	2.9	56	2.9	63	2.2
	<i>N(10,1)</i>	49	1.9	73	2.6	46	2.0	66	2.3	53	2.5	58	2.1
	<i>N(20,1)</i>	50	2.5	71	3.1	48	2.2	64	1.7	46	1.9	55	1.9
40	<i>N(5,1)</i>	52	2.2	74	2.7	52	2.2	65	2.6	52	2.5	62	1.8
	<i>N(10,1)</i>	47	1.4	71	2.1	50	2.5	66	2.7	48	2.2	58	2.1
	<i>N(20,1)</i>	50	3.5	74	3.2	50	3.4	67	2.3	46	3.1	62	2.5
50	<i>N(5,1)</i>	48	3.1	51	2.6	48	1.4	61	1.7	49	1.6	57	2.5
	<i>N(10,1)</i>	46	1.7	49	1.5	45	2.0	67	1.7	52	2.1	59	2.8
	<i>N(20,1)</i>	49	2.5	50	1.6	47	2.1	61	2.3	49	2.6	56	2.3
60	<i>N(5,1)</i>	50	2.2	69	3.4	50	3.2	67	3.8	52	2.2	60	2.4
	<i>N(10,1)</i>	51	1.6	74	2.7	51	2.5	66	1.5	49	2.0	57	2.0
	<i>N(20,1)</i>	47	1.9	70	2.4	48	1.5	64	1.3	46	1.1	57	2.0
<i>Average</i>		51	2	72	3	51	2	65	3	51	2	60	2

Table 2 showed the simulation results when 10% of the files were contaminated. Under the column 5% of files trimmed, the percentage of matches of the Classical Matching and the Trimmed Record were the same, being equal to 49% and with a standard error (SE) of 2. However, for the 10% of files trimmed column, the percentage of matches using the Trimmed Record, with a percentage of matched records equal to 64% and with an SE of 2, was higher compared to the other matching method whose average percentage of matched records equal to 49%, and with an SE of 2. The 10% trimmed files column has a greater percentage of matched records as compared to the 20% of the files trimmed. Again, this implies that the Trimmed Record performs better when the percentage of contaminated files will be equal to the percentage of files trimmed. Here, it was also observed that in the two statistical methods, the percentage of matched records decreased as the percentage of variables being contaminated were increased. Although, with the same percentage of variables being contaminated and the same percentage of files trimmed, it was observed that the percentage of the matched records, for the two statistical methods, has decreased when the mean of the contaminants increased from 5 to 20, thus, this implies that percentage of matched records will decrease when the contaminants to the variables will increase.

Table 3 showed the simulation results when 20% of the files were contaminated. The Trimmed Record method gave significantly higher percentage of matches, when 20% of the files were trimmed, as compared to the classical method, however, when 5% and 10% of the files were trimmed, gave the same percentage of matches (on the average) as compared to the Classical Matching method. Here, the Classical method and the Trimmed Record method on the average, have percentage of matched records equal to 45%, on the 5% and 10% of the files being trimmed, respectively, with a standard error of 2, however, when 20% of the files were trimmed, the Trimmed Record method gave 54% of matched records with a standard error of 2 while the Classical method gave 44% of matched records with a standard error of 2. This implies that, the Trimmed Record method performs better when 20% of the files were trimmed and with 20% of the files being contaminated.

Table 2. 10% of the Files Being Contaminated

Percent of Variables Being Contaminated	Distribution of Contaminants	5 % of Files Trimmed						10 % of Files Trimmed						20 % of Files Trimmed					
		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method			
		%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE		
10	N(5,1)	60	2.3	60	2.1	58	3.4	62	2.2	54	2.3	56	1.5						
	N(10,1)	50	2.4	49	2.7	53	2.1	66	3.1	49	1.9	55	2.4						
	N(20,1)	47	2.1	45	1.4	51	1.9	63	1.9	48	1.1	59	1.9						
20	N(5,1)	52	1.7	56	1.9	53	2.4	62	2.5	48	2.1	64	1.8						
	N(10,1)	51	1.7	50	2.3	51	2.3	64	2.2	51	2.4	60	2.0						
	N(20,1)	46	1.9	45	1.7	51	2.0	67	2.9	48	1.2	57	1.9						
30	N(5,1)	49	2.4	54	2.8	47	2.7	64	2.2	48	2.8	58	2.8						
	N(10,1)	46	2.0	45	1.9	48	1.7	65	2.7	51	2.1	59	1.3						
	N(20,1)	46	2.5	45	2.2	47	1.7	64	2.0	49	1.9	59	1.5						
40	N(5,1)	50	1.4	52	2.2	43	1.9	61	3.2	49	2.4	65	2.8						
	N(10,1)	47	2.3	48	2.3	44	2.7	64	2.1	47	1.7	61	2.3						
	N(20,1)	49	1.1	49	2.2	46	2.3	66	1.7	43	1.6	58	2.6						
50	N(5,1)	48	3.1	51	2.6	48	1.4	61	1.7	49	1.6	57	2.5						
	N(10,1)	46	1.7	49	1.5	45	2.0	67	1.7	52	2.1	59	2.8						
	N(20,1)	49	2.5	50	1.6	47	2.1	61	2.3	49	2.6	56	2.3						
60	N(5,1)	49	2.1	53	2.3	48	2.9	59	2.8	46	1.6	57	3.0						
	N(10,1)	46	1.9	47	2.2	47	2.5	65	2.5	48	1.3	62	2.4						
	N(20,1)	47	2.2	45	1.9	44	1.5	64	1.3	48	3.8	59	3.5						
Average		49	2	49	2	48	2	64	2	49	2	59	2						

Table 3. 20% of the Files Being Contaminated

Percent of Variables Being Contaminated	Distribution of Contaminants	5 % of Files Trimmed						10 % of Files Trimmed						20 % of Files Trimmed					
		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method		Classical Method		Trimmed Record Method			
		%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE	%M	SE		
10	N(5,1)	54	2.0	51	2.7	50	3.3	52	3.2	49	2.7	54	3.0						
	N(10,1)	47	2.4	46	2.2	51	2.5	49	2.9	48	2.1	54	2.1						
	N(20,1)	50	2.8	50	2.1	50	2.7	47	1.8	44	1.2	56	2.1						
20	N(5,1)	49	1.7	48	2.1	48	2.7	47	2.5	45	2.3	55	3.3						
	N(10,1)	47	2.4	49	2.4	48	3.0	44	3.2	46	2.4	54	2.7						
	N(20,1)	42	1.9	43	2.2	47	1.0	45	2.0	48	1.7	58	1.9						
30	N(5,1)	45	2.0	45	2.3	40	1.7	43	1.3	42	1.3	52	2.2						
	N(10,1)	44	1.9	42	1.3	45	1.4	47	1.9	42	1.6	51	2.0						
	N(20,1)	47	1.7	44	1.6	45	2.1	42	1.5	45	3.2	58	2.2						
40	N(5,1)	44	2.9	44	2.1	44	2.3	45	2.6	43	2.5	52	1.7						
	N(10,1)	45	0.9	43	0.8	42	1.5	45	2.4	41	2.3	53	3.0						
	N(20,1)	45	2.2	46	1.5	47	1.2	46	1.7	44	1.7	57	3.0						
50	N(5,1)	41	1.3	41	1.5	43	2.8	43	2.4	42	2.2	52	2.1						
	N(10,1)	42	1.7	42	1.8	40	1.3	42	2.0	41	1.9	55	2.3						
	N(20,1)	42	2.1	43	1.9	42	1.0	42	1.7	44	2.7	59	2.2						
60	N(5,1)	43	1.4	42	1.8	40	1.6	41	2.1	40	1.3	53	1.9						
	N(10,1)	43	1.8	42	2.0	40	1.3	40	1.5	40	2.2	55	1.3						
	N(20,1)	40	1.7	43	1.7	43	1.6	43	0.8	42	2.0	51	2.3						
Average		45	2	45	2	45	2	45	2	45	2	44	2	54	2				

CONCLUSION

The highest percentage of matches using the 2 methods of matching were shown in table 1 when there was 5% of the files being contaminated with 5% trimming of files being done. From the 3 tables, it was observed that there was a bigger difference in the percentage of matches between the Classical Matching method and the Trimmed Record Method, further, the Trimmed Record Method is better than the Classical Matching method.

In this study, the Trimmed Record is a robust statistical matching method. This method is not so much affected when the files were being corrupted, thus, gave higher percentage of records matched as compared to the Classical Matching method. Further, analytic investigation of this robust procedure of doing statistical matching revealed qualitative description of the increase in the matched records for corrupted files whereas the simulation results gave numerical estimate of the matched records.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the context of this study, supposedly 2 identical files were reconciled but some records of the files were corrupted. Hence, contamination of some records will affect the matches of the supposedly identical files. In the real situation, we don't know that the files were corrupted or not. Investigation of the Trimmed Record method, showed that as the number of records in a file that are being contaminated becomes infinite, the covariance of the files when using the Trimmed Record method will approach the covariance of the files when the Classical Matching method was used, hence, implying that, the percentage of matches using the Trimmed Record method will approach the percentage of matched records using the Classical method. With this, it would be better to use the Trimmed Record in matching of two identical files .

The Trimmed Record method in fusing two identical files finds application in reconciling 2 sets of records, hence, this could be used to reconcile the records of the burned records of the National Statistics Office or even reconciling the records of the Commission on Elections.

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